

Viewpoint

AI in Primary Care: Frameworks, Challenges, and Guardrails

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Summary

Artificial intelligence (AI) is already reshaping many aspects of primary care from documentation and triage to population health planning, but implementation remains fragmented, uneven, and often poorly aligned with the realities of frontline services. This Viewpoint proposes a functional framework for categorising AI applications in primary care, using the WHO Digital Health Interventions taxonomy as a foundation. We argue that taking a system-level approach allows clearer identification of implementation gaps, regulatory needs, and areas of maturity. Drawing on this structure, we examine technical, ethical, operational challenges and propose a set of high-level principles to guide safe, equitable, and sustainable AI integration. We conclude by highlighting the need for stronger governance and participatory approaches to ensure that AI strengthens, rather than fragments, the core values of primary care.

Introduction

Globally, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming healthcare. From its origins as a set of rule-based systems to today's generative models, this technology has opened new possibilities around how healthcare is delivered and experienced.¹ Primary care - which can deliver up to 90% of all essential health services globally² - is a natural setting for AI integration. The potential benefits are substantial: improving diagnostic accuracy, optimising workflows, and mitigating workforce shortages by supporting clinicians and self-care at scale. This Viewpoint explores AI's potential applications in global primary care, then introduces a system-level framework to classify AI tools, examines core challenges, and finally proposes five guardrails for safe, equitable and sustainable use. While AI in healthcare is often discussed in abstract terms, its impact will ultimately be felt in everyday encounters between patients and clinicians. We begin with two plausible near-future scenarios of how AI might shape primary care in contrasting contexts (Panel 1).

Panel 1: Two plausible near-future scenarios of AI-augmented primary care **UK General Practice**

A 65-year-old smoker uses the AI-enabled NHS app to report a new, persistent cough with blood-stained phlegm. The integrated chatbot conducts an initial assessment, asking structured follow-up questions and reviewing the patient's medical record for relevant history and investigations. Based on this, the system books a same-day blood test with a healthcare assistant, a chest x-ray at the local diagnostic centre, and an urgent consultation with the patient's usual GP. Prior to the consultation, the GP receives an AI-generated summary of the presenting complaint, flagged risk factors, and suggested differential diagnoses. During the appointment, ambient AI software transcribes the consultation in real time, generating prompts around possible red-flag symptoms, evidence-based guideline recommendations, and appropriate investigation bundles. The GP can choose whether or not to engage with these suggestions. After finalising the management plan, the GP reviews and edits the AI-generated consultation notes before approving them. A related tool then generates a patient-facing summary and links to further information, which are sent via SMS following GP approval.

Rural Botswana

In a remote village, a five-year-old boy develops a fever and rash. His mother borrows a

neighbour's smartphone to access an online telemedicine platform. She describes her son's symptoms in her local dialect using speech-to-text, and the AI system responds with clarifying questions in the same language, also requesting photographs of the rash via the phone's camera. The AI triage tool generates a preliminary list of differential diagnoses and a risk assessment. A remote clinician, supported by AI-driven decision support, reviews the case via video-link and advises that the boy be seen by the local community health worker (CHW). The system forwards a structured summary and a link to the relevant diagnostic pathway to the CHW's mobile phone. When the boy is reviewed later that day, the CHW enters vital signs into the AI tool, which generates a suggested management plan and tailored safety-netting advice. The boy is automatically added to the schedule for the mobile clinic's next visit, enabling in-person follow-up, medication management, and non-urgent laboratory tests to be collected. Appointment details are sent by text to the mother, and the case is flagged within district surveillance systems for monitoring.

These scenarios raise a series of challenges that need to be addressed. First, we will survey the evolution of AI in healthcare and how frameworks can help us make sense of the contemporary landscape.

The evolution of AI in healthcare

AI in healthcare has evolved significantly over the past decades, progressing from early rule-based 'expert systems' to modern generative models.³ This evolution reflects advances in computing power, data availability, and algorithmic sophistication. In primary care - where clinical complexity is high, data are messy, and patient needs are diverse,⁴ strict AI tools might be best thought of in terms of tools for specific tasks rather than wholesale replacements for clinicians, broadly configured to perform; task automation (e.g. for documentation and coding); pattern identification to find associations and enable predictions (e.g. forecasting and risk stratification); and content generation (e.g. generating text, images or sound to inform clinical care drawing on vast amounts of existing data). We currently face a fragmented federation of different tools across these domains.

AI applications can be grouped into four overlapping *technical* categories: rule-based systems, machine learning (including deep learning), natural language processing (NLP), and generative AI (Figure 1). Rule-based systems are the earliest form of AI in medicine, dating back to the 1950s &

1960s.⁵ These rely on manually encoded ‘if-then’ logic derived from clinical guidelines and remain foundational in many electronic health records (EHRs). Whilst these tools lack the ability to adapt and learn, their transparency and reliability make them indispensable for tasks such as generating drug-interaction alerts, vaccination prompts, and routine screening reminders. They still form the scaffolding for many of the more advanced AI approaches.

Machine learning (ML) emerged in the 1980s and 1990s, gaining momentum in medical research in the 2000s as digital health data became increasingly abundant.⁶ ML systems use statistical models to detect patterns and make predictions from data. Most commonly, ML involves *supervised learning*, where models are trained on labelled datasets (e.g. to predict the likelihood of a patient being admitted to hospital using labelled variables from primary care EHR data). *Unsupervised learning*, by contrast, uses unlabelled data to uncover hidden structures, such as clustering patients with complex multimorbidity. *Reinforcement learning* takes a different tack: models learn by trial and error, adjusting their actions based on feedback from their environment. ML tools can be *static* - trained once and left alone - or *adaptive*, continually updating as new data arrives.

Deep learning is a subfield of machine learning that uses multi-layered artificial neural networks to model more complex, non-linear relationships in data.⁷ It gained prominence in the 2010s with image and speech recognition. In healthcare, deep learning powers diagnostic tools e.g. that can classify images or analyse heart sounds.⁸ The strength of deep learning lies in high-dimensional pattern recognition, but its ‘black-box’ nature makes outputs harder to interpret, as the underlying chain of reasoning can’t be interrogated in the same way as an ‘if-then’ algorithm. This is particularly important for approaches that push new boundaries in the field of prediction which are not strictly auditable, such as risk factor ascertainment based on retinal images,⁹ diabetes screening based on chest x-rays,¹⁰ and using ECGs to identify kidney disease.¹¹

Natural language processing (NLP) has advanced in parallel, focusing on extracting meaning from unstructured text such as consultation notes, referral letters, discharge summaries, and audio recordings of consultations.¹² Early systems used rule-based or dictionary approaches to generate intelligible text, whilst newer approaches use deep learning to structure clinical narratives, support coding, and generate summaries. NLP can play a critical role in converting messy primary care records into analysable data, which is valuable both for care and research.

Generative AI (GenAI), the most recent development, builds on deep learning and NLP to produce new content.¹³ Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT from OpenAI, Claude from Anthropic, and Gemini from Google are trained on vast bodies of data (contentiously – often without the owners' permission¹⁴) and are capable of generating responses, drafting documentation, and interacting with patients through chatbot interfaces. Their outputs are based on predictions of the next most likely word, but can be impressively fluent. At the same time, GenAI models are prone to hallucination (where they make up information), bias, and unpredictable behaviour.^{15,16} Despite these limitations, GenAI holds transformative potential for primary care.

Looking beyond current tools, the trend is toward more 'agentic' AI systems.¹⁷ These are not merely integrated tools following a fixed workflow, but autonomous agents capable of pursuing high-level clinical goals by planning and executing multi-step tasks. For example, an agent tasked to 'work-up a patient newly diagnosed with hypertension' might autonomously schedule appointments, order lab tests, draft educational materials, and could even run subsequent machine learning risk prediction tools. This paradigm of goal-directed autonomy raises a host of new challenges around oversight, safety, medicolegal accountability, and clinical responsibility, which will require new governance models.

Even without agentic systems, many contemporary AI clinical applications already blend multiple techniques. A health chatbot might use NLP to interpret text input, machine learning to classify risk, and generative AI to formulate a response. This functional overlap mirrors the integrated, multifaceted nature of primary care itself. To make sense of this rapidly evolving landscape, it is often more helpful to think about AI in terms of clinical functions rather than technical groups.

Figure 1: A simplified representation of the AI landscape

Note: GenAI: Generative AI, including large language models

Frameworks

Efforts to classify AI use cases in healthcare have typically fallen into four broad approaches. Some focus on the technical method i.e. categorising systems by whether they rely on machine learning, natural language processing, or generative models.^{18,19} Others group AI applications by clinical function, such as diagnosis, triage, or prescribing;²⁰ others by workflow stage e.g. providing support pre-consultation, during the consultation, or post-consultation;²¹ or by applying a stakeholder lens e.g. Lin et al.’s seminal framework that mapped AI applications across ten ‘problem spaces’ aligned with patients, providers, and payers/employers.²²

While each has value, these approaches are limited in important ways. Technical categorisations of underlying technology (i.e. ML vs GenAI) aren’t particularly helpful in the consultation room. Function-based typologies can be overly broad and lack granularity, and workflow-based models

struggle to accommodate tools that cut across multiple stages of care. They are also tied to specific organisational workflows that might not translate across different contexts. Stakeholder-based categories offer useful perspectives, but we are concerned that they are not easily mappable to system-level governance, regulation, or procurement decisions. Importantly, few models account for health system responsibilities as laid out in widely accepted architectural frameworks.

To address this gap, we have mapped AI common use cases in primary care against the *2019 WHO Digital Health Interventions Framework* (Table 2).²³ Adopted by many national digital health strategies, the WHO framework categorises digital health interventions according to the functions they perform for four core user groups: clients, health workers, health system managers, and data services. Each function is coded and nested, allowing alignment with financing, supply chain, and governance systems. This system-level focus makes it particularly suitable for primary care, where implementation decisions must sit within broader health system responsibilities. In populating the table with examples, we were aware that the term ‘intelligence’ is being applied to a wide range of tools that range from advanced applications of deep learning to simple algorithms. We also note that a recent scoping review found that half of all identified papers on AI in primary care described tools that were in the ideation or development stages, with less than 10% of all papers presenting findings from mature tools that had been deployed within clinical practice.²⁴

Table 2: AI Use Cases Mapped to WHO Digital Health Interventions

Stakeholder	Function	Potential AI use case examples
Client	1.1.2 Transmit targeted health information to client(s) based on health status or demographics	AI-personalised SMS for high-risk groups based on EHR data; Behaviour-specific nudges; Automated reminders for chronic disease reviews, vaccines, or screening, triggered by AI generated risk scores
	1.2.1 Transmit untargeted health information to an undefined population	Generic health alerts during outbreaks via SMS or social media bots
	1.3.1 Peer group for clients	AI-moderated patient forums and peer-matching platforms
	1.4.2 Self-monitoring of health or diagnostic data by client	Wearables for analysing heart rate, sleep, or glucose; Behavioural nudges
	1.5.2 Reporting of public health events by clients	Symptom checkers logging structured self-reported data
	1.6.1 Client look-up of health information	24/7 AI chatbots for health queries; FAQ-based LLM interfaces
Health Worker	2.1.1 Verify client unique identity	Biometric ID verification; adaptable patient registration forms
	2.2.2 Manage client's structured clinical records	Summarisation of EHRs; auto-linking of past notes and test results
	2.2.3 Manage client's unstructured clinical records	Generate consultation summaries based on free text in the patient record and audio recordings of clinical consultations
	2.3.1 Provide prompts and alerts based according to protocol	Prompts suggesting appropriate diagnoses, investigations and treatment options
	2.3.3 Screen clients by risk or other health status	Triage support; differential diagnosis suggestions; point-of-care alerts (e.g. cancer risk, allergies)
	2.4.1 Consultations between remote client and health worker	AI-assisted scheduling and routing; real-time transcription tools for teleconsults

	2.5.4 Transmit non-routine health event alerts to health worker(s)	Routing referrals and internal messages based on urgency or topic using NLP triage
	2.6.2 Manage referrals between points of service within health sector	Auto-generated referral letters with triaged urgency flags
	2.7.2 Schedule health worker's activities	AI-predicted no-show rates; clinician workload balancing
	2.8.1 Provide training content to health worker(s)	AI-driven personalised learning modules with feedback
	2.9.1 Transmit or track prescription orders	Automated medication reviews; dose adjustment suggestions; drug interaction alerts
	* Interpret digitally captured data	AI interpretation of ECGs, skin lesions, retinal images
Health System Manager	3.1.2 Monitor performance of health worker(s)	Predictive workforce planning based on service data
	3.2.1 Manage inventory and distribution of health commodities	AI-predicted stockouts and automated resupply orders
	3.3.1 Notification of public health events from point of diagnosis	Real-time flagging of notifiable diseases; syndromic surveillance; Anomaly detection for new patterns (e.g. unusual fever clusters or prescribing spikes)
	*Equity monitoring and service gap analysis	Dashboards highlighting underserved populations; care gap analytics stratified by geography or demographic factors
Data Services	4.1.4 Automated analysis of data to generate new information or predictions on future events	NLP extraction from free-text notes; AI dashboards for health trends
	4.2.3 Classify disease codes or cause of mortality	Auto-coding diagnoses, lab data, or correspondence using ML
	4.3.1 Map location of health facilities/structures	Geospatial ML to detect coverage gaps or optimise site placement
	4.4.1 Data exchange across systems	AI reconciliation of conflicting data formats or record duplicates

*Function not included in the WHO Digital Health Intervention Framework

This framework provides a scaffold for assessing where AI is currently being deployed, where oversight or evidence is needed, and where investment might be most impactful. It also allows comparison of maturity across different domains (e.g. triage vs documentation) and highlights where current frameworks fall short; for example, the lack of explicit domains for diagnostic interpretation or equity monitoring. By grounding AI in the WHO framework, we emphasise that AI is not a single, monolithic ‘solution’, but a collection of tools and functions spanning patient education, triage, documentation, workforce management, and more. In practice, these tools will be layered and combined within workflows, often behind the scenes.

Despite these strengths, the WHO framework has some important limitations; the current iteration does not include a domain for tools that *interpret* digitally captured data, and it lacks a focus on equity monitoring. We have added these domains under the Health Worker and Health System manager stakeholder groupings respectively. Importantly, the framework does not account for approaches that link multiple tools, which will be the core value-add of emerging agentic systems.²⁵ Mapping AI use cases onto the WHO Digital Health Interventions framework highlights both the breadth of current activity and the blind spots in existing taxonomies. But classification alone does not resolve the deeper uncertainties raised by our near-future scenarios from Botswana and the UK.

Challenges

Primary care is a demanding environment and our scenarios illustrate a number of challenges that must be addressed to ensure that AI tools are implemented safely, fairly, and sustainably. Whilst many of these issues are not unique to primary care, the relational, decentralised, and data-fragmented nature of primary care means that the risks and consequences of failure may be particularly acute. Drawing on existing from evidence in the fields of AI, Information and Communication Technology and Implementation Science we group challenges into three broad domains: technical, operational, and ethical & social.

Technical challenges relate to how AI systems are trained, validated, and deployed. Bias is a key concern: models built on incomplete or skewed data can systematically misclassify, under-diagnose, or exclude populations—especially those already marginalised.²⁶ This is particularly problematic for predictive tools that guide triage or resource allocation, raising

questions about how we ensure that training data are truly representative. Explainability is another limitation, especially for deep learning systems where outputs are opaque even to developers.²⁷ Without transparency, errors become harder to identify, challenge, or correct, which leads to uncomfortable questions about whether we should hold AI to a stricter standard of error than we accept for human clinicians and where liability lies. Closely related is the issue of robustness: many models perform well in curated test environments but falter when exposed to messy real-world primary care data. Interoperability presents an additional hurdle: for AI to function safely across the care continuum, it must integrate with a wide array of health IT systems and datasets, which are often fragmented or poorly standardised.²⁸

Ethical and social challenges are equally pressing. Accountability is a central issue: who is legally responsible for errors when clinical decisions are influenced- or even drafted - by AI?²⁹

The prospect of shifting tasks to “technicians” who collect data for AI triage raises further concerns about professional roles and tacit skills: what, if anything, do clinicians lose by foregoing the process of taking histories or writing their own notes? Over-reliance on AI risks de-skilling the workforce, creating a strategic vulnerability in the event of outages or cyber-attacks. Autonomy and consent also need safeguarding: patients must know when AI is being used in their care, have the option to opt out, and trust that sensitive data are secure despite dependence on multiple tools from different organisations, including for-profit companies. Equity is another critical concern: does embedding these systems advance a digital-only model of care that risks entrenching inequalities, or can they be deployed to close gaps? Patient experience is central—are AI prompts helpful or intrusive, and how do patients perceive clinicians’ reliance on algorithmic support? Finally, environmental sustainability is an ethical dimension often overlooked: what are the implications of embedding energy-intensive models into everyday practice?

Operational and governance challenges cut across funding, regulation, and workforce preparedness. Upfront costs are substantial, and health systems, particularly in low-resource settings, may lack the infrastructure to deploy tools safely. Regulatory frameworks are still evolving, and existing guidance is poorly matched to the complexity of modern AI. Monitoring, auditability, and version control are rarely standardised. Procurement is often driven by vendor relationships or legacy pilots rather than systematic evaluation, raising risks of fragmentation and duplication.³⁰ Most importantly, there remains a critical gap in

workforce readiness. Clinicians do not need to become programmers, but they do need a new form of AI literacy: the ability to critically appraise algorithmic performance, understand validation contexts, and recognise when outputs are untrustworthy.³¹ Just as with the D-dimer blood test to screen for deep vein thrombosis, highly sensitive but only meaningful in low-risk contexts, safe use of AI depends on nuanced understanding of its strengths and limits. AI models may also silently degrade through ‘model drift’ as patient populations, clinical practices, or data patterns change with reference to the original training dataset.³² Most importantly, unlike a lab test, an AI can embed societal bias from its training data.^{34,35} Therefore, training clinicians is not a 'soft' requirement but a central pillar of safety, equipping them to oversee complex, dynamic, and potentially biased systems. Moreover, the ability to craft effective prompts for AI tools is becoming an essential skill for healthcare professionals.^{36,37}

While we have grouped challenges and guardrails thematically, many of the issues are not neatly siloed. In practice, several deeper tensions cut across technical, ethical, and operational domains, shaping how AI is implemented, regulated, and experienced. Panel 2 summarises these tensions at a glance.

Panel 2: Tensions

Tension	
Local relevance vs global scale	AI tools that work well in one country or health system may fail elsewhere if not adapted; governance needs to allow local tailoring.
Automation vs clinical agency	Automating tasks can improve efficiency but must not erode professional judgement or the trust patients place in their clinicians.
Innovation vs accountability	AI often reaches clinics faster than regulation can keep up, creating grey zones over who is liable when things go wrong.
Efficiency vs equity	Systems designed to maximise speed and throughput may leave behind patients with complex needs or incomplete records.
Performance vs transparency	Complex AI models may deliver high accuracy, but their “black box” nature makes them hard to interpret or adapt, particularly in multilingual or resource-constrained settings.

Building on these challenges, we propose five guardrails, grounded in the WHO’s ethical principles for AI in health,³⁸ the Starfield Signal road map for AI in primary care,³⁹ the Society of General Internal Medicine position statement,⁴⁰ a BMJ evaluation paper,⁴¹ and emerging reporting standards (such as SPIRIT-AI,⁴² DECIDE-AI,⁴³ and CONSORT-AI,⁴⁴ TRIPOD-AI,⁴⁵

PROBAST-AI⁴⁶) and broader literatures in clinical informatics, human–computer interaction, and implementation science:^{47–49}

- **Contextual fit**

AI tools must be validated in the settings where they are used, with representative training data, patient populations, and staff. Models proven in American tertiary hospitals may fail in other settings unless adapted. Tools should reduce (rather than add to) friction in workflows, and align with the core attributes of primary care: first-contact, continuity, comprehensiveness, coordination, and person-centredness.⁵⁰ Clinicians must be involved throughout the innovation lifecycle and that training/support are essential.

- **Transparency**

Outputs must be interpretable and actionable for clinicians, patients, and regulators. Recommendations must be accompanied by context that allows clinicians and patients to judge their reliability and act safely when errors occur. Where high-performing models are opaque, their limits and safe-use boundaries must be explicit. Even if the inner workings of LLMs remain opaque, transparency should be mandatory regarding the data they are trained on, their performance characteristics, and their intended use.

- **Inclusivity**

Evaluation should monitor subgroup performance and bias over time, ensuring that marginalised groups are not disadvantaged. Data sources must be representative, and outcomes reported transparently. Patient-facing consent and literacy tools should be available in multiple languages and accessible formats. Patients, clinicians, and communities should ideally be involved in co-development, governance, and oversight of AI tools in primary care.

- **Accountability**

Liability for AI-influenced decisions must be clearly defined. Human override and audit trails are non-negotiable, particularly where AI influences triage, diagnosis, or treatment. Risk assessments should take a long-term view and consider the impact

on workforce displacement. Accountability frameworks should clarify the respective roles of clinicians, vendors, and regulators.

- **Sustainability**

AI adoption must be financially, operationally, and environmentally sustainable.

Planning should include model retraining, technical support, resilience against outages, and monitoring for drift. Costs and benefits should be reported alongside environmental impacts, especially for energy-intensive generative models.

Innovative payment models are needed to make AI adoption feasible for small and under-resourced providers.

Taken together, these principles aim to support deliberate, context-sensitive evaluation of AI in primary care. They do not replace technical appraisal but sit alongside it, ensuring that the tools we adopt are not only powerful but useful, equitable, and safe.

Conclusion

In the words of William Gibson, “the future is already here, it is just not very evenly distributed”.⁵¹ Algorithmically-driven high-risk alert pop-ups are already an (often irritating) part of daily practice in high-income settings, as are population health management tools, AI scribes, and numerous other technologies. The question is not whether AI will be used, but whether it will reinforce or erode the core values of primary care: continuity, comprehensiveness, first-contact access, coordination, and person-centredness.

In this Viewpoint we have made three contributions. First, we show through near-future scenarios how AI may reshape frontline encounters in both high- and low-resource settings, surfacing questions of safety, accountability, equity, and patient experience. Second, we map AI applications to the WHO Digital Health Interventions framework, offering a system-level structure that makes visible both opportunities and blind spots. Third, we synthesise existing guidance and wider informatics and implementation literature into five guardrail principles; contextual fit, transparency, inclusivity, accountability, and sustainability. These translate high-level concerns into operational criteria for evaluation and governance.

Our central message is simple: whilst the use of AI in primary care seems inevitable, the value of these tools is far from assured. Without deliberate governance, inclusive design, and

clinician and patient involvement, these tools risk fragmenting care, entrenching inequities, and displacing professional judgement. However, with appropriate guardrails, they can potentially preserve the relational core of primary care whilst extending access to high quality care.

Search strategy and selection criteria

We reviewed English-language literature and policy documents that were identified through targeted searches of PubMed and grey literature sources, focusing on synonyms for artificial intelligence AND primary care. The searches were conducted on multiple days over six months, between March and September 2025, as part of wider internet searches for an evolving set of keywords and terms as different coauthors brought new concepts and ideas to the Viewpoint.

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Use of generative AI

We used ChatGPT (Edu) 5.0 for idea generation and drafting initial content on the evolution of AI section. All content was reviewed, and ultimately re-written by the team. We also used AI to perform a synthetic peer-review of the draft manuscript to identify potential errors, omissions, and areas that needed to be strengthened. This feedback informed our final revision.

Declarations

BMS serves as part-time chief information officer of Engage Mx, a South African healthcare technology company developing clinical workflow automation and population health analytics platforms. He is also a clinical AI consultant of Phylaxis.ai, a company focused on machine learning applications for clinical triage and risk stratification for Sub-Saharan Africa. The other authors declared no conflicts of interest.

Contributions

LNA conceptualised the Viewpoint and wrote the first draft. LMP contributed to the development of the themes. LMP and JL reviewed and revised the second draft. LNA, LMP,

and JL performed data collection and analysis. BMS, KN, and DB reviewed and edited subsequent drafts. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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